

A Study of Gender disparity in the workforce in Kaimur district, Bihar

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Gender disparity in the workforce has always been a hurdle in the overall economic development. The poor presence of women in the galleries of economy can be seen as a result of disproportionate share of their engagement in household and caregiving responsibilities. The situation is even more deplorable in the rural areas where the societal norms, history of oppression and lack of diversification of economy creates a bleak atmosphere for promoting women in the work force. The disparity in terms of gender is more pronounced in states like Bihar who have their own problems regarding growth trajectory with low per capita income, highest poverty rate and an appallingly low literacy rate. The present study aims at understanding the gap between the two genders in the population in the terms of main workers, marginal workers and non-workers in a kaimur district of Bihar. The work participation rate is low in the area. The analysis of the disparity in all the eleven blocks will help in throwing light on the employment scenario.

Keywords-: *Gender disparity, Working population, Main workers, Marginal workers, Non-workers.*

Introduction

In India, the participation of women in the labour force is remarkably lower as compared to developed economies where its more balanced. We are blessed with a unique demographic advantage with a large percentage of the population in the working age group resulting into a lower dependency ratio. This demographic dividend gets marred due to a relatively low female work participation rate. Women are solely responsible for domestic chores and spend a longer time in care economy as compared to men. This leaves them with much less time for employment in the various sectors of economy. The deeply embedded social norms and gender stereotyping often pose limit on the occupational choices of women. Another barrier which discourages the entry of women in workforce is crime against them at the workplace. Kaimur is one of the 38 districts of Bihar and has been acknowledged as an underdeveloped region and listed in the country's most backward 250 districts in 2006.

The chief causes of its backwardness can be credited to its geographical isolation, dependence on agriculture, socio-structural setbacks etc.

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About the district

Kaimur is the western district of the state, with a distinct geographic, economic and cultural background. It covers an area of 3362 square Kilometres. The district is bounded in the north by Rohtas in east and south and by Buxar in north east. The study area is subdivided into two subdivisions namely Bhabua and Mohania which are further divided into eleven blocks. There are 1695 villages in the area of which 1337 are inhabited. The Kaimur range and Rohtas plateau cover the southern part of the district. The Karmanasa and Durgawati rivers run through the district.

The total population of the area according to census 2011 is 16,26,384 out of which 8,47,006 are males and 7,79,378 are females. The decadal growth rate for 2001 to 2011 was 27.50 percent which is higher than the decadal growth rate of state. The population density in the district is 488 persons per square kilometre, which is the lowest in state (1106 persons per square kilometre). This implies that the pressure of population on the land is not very high. The sex ratio is 920 which is two points higher than that of state. The population in the age group of 0 to 6 years is 2,99,281 of which 1,54,105 are males and 1,45,176 are females. The total population of scheduled caste in the area is 3,69,088 and the total population of scheduled tribe is 57,981.

Objectives

The main objectives of the present study are :-

1. 1.To study the male and female differential in Main workers.
2. 2.To study the male and female differential in Marginal worker.
3. 3.To study the male and female differential in Non- workers.

Methodology

The study has been based on secondary data obtained from District Census Handbook of the year 2011. The gender gap in the work force, Main, Marginal and Non workers have been calculated and listed in the form of table. The analysis of the gender gap across the blocks has been displayed by the help of choropleth maps.

Working population in the district

The district has a total working population of 5,11,163 which constitute 31.43 percent of the total population of the study area. The blocks with larger number of workers are Bhabua, Mohania and Chainpur. The blocks display a wide variation in the gap between the percentage of male and female workers. Table no. 1 shows block wise male and female differential in workforce in the area. The highest gap was noticed in Bhabua (57.55) followed by Durgawati (55.38) and Kudra (50.1). The lowest Gap was found in Adhaura (18.99)

Table 1: Block wise Male-female Differential of Workforce in Kaimur District (2011)

S. No	Area	Total workers	Male workers (%)	Female Workers (%)	Gender Gap
	District	511163	73.55	26.45	47.1
1	Ramgarh	42879	71.85	28.16	43.69
2	Nuaon	34971	71.99	28.00	43.99
3	Kudra	50825	75.55	25.45	50.1
4	Mohania	64807	78.5	21.50	57
5	Durgawati	39352	77.7	22.32	55.38
6	Chand	46355	67.8	32.17	35.63
7	Chainpur	64476	67.75	32.25	35.5
8	Bhabua	73475	78.77	21.22	57.55
9	Rampur	27979	72.36	27.65	44.71
10	Bhagwanpur	20869	73.5	26.53	46.97
11	Adhaura	24707	59.18	40.81	18.99

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

If all the blocks are categorised into low, moderate and high gender differential in the working force, then it's observed that only Adhaura (18.99) falls in low category. Two blocks Chainpur (35.5) and Chand (35.63) fall in the category of moderate gender gap. Majority of the blocks fall in the category of high differential above 40. They are Ramgarh (43.69), Nuaon (43.99), Rampur (44.71), Bhagwanpur (46.97), Kudra (50.1), Durgawati (55.38), Mohania (57), and Bhabua (57.55)

Table 2: Category of Male-female Differential in Workforce (2011)

Male female differential	Range	No. of Blocks	Blocks
Low	<20	1	Adhaura
Moderate	20-40	2	Chainpur, Chand
High	>40	8	Ramgarh, Nuaon, Kudra, Mohania, Durgawati, Bhabua, Rampur, Bhagwanpur

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

Male and Female Differential in Main workers

The total population of main workers in the district is 2,84,646. The male main workers and female main workers are 2,35,244 (82.65%) and 49,402 (17.35%) respectively. The highest percentage of female main workers to the total population of the main workers was highest in Adhaura (30.6%). The lowest percentage was found in Mohania (11%)

Table 3: Block wise Male-female Differential in Main Workers in Kaimur District (2011)

Serial number	Area	Main workers	Male workers (%)	Female Workers (%)	Gender Gap
	District	284646	82.65	17.35	65.3
1	Ramgarh	20697	84.69	22	62.69
2	Nuaon	22221	78.06	22	56.06
3	Kudra	30010	85.5	14.5	71
4	Mohania	36913	89.2	11	78.2
5	Durgawati	22983	85.72	14.28	71.44
6	Chand	27067	74.5	25.5	49
7	Chainpur	39014	77.5	22.5	55
8	Bhabua	38388	86.27	14	72.3
9	Rampur	14119	84	16	68
10	Bhagwanpur	17088	78.3	21.7	56.6
11	Adhaura	6664	69.41	30.59	39

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

All the blocks can be divided into three groups. The gap on the basis of gender is very high in the case of main workers. Only Adhaura had moderate difference in the male and female marginal workers. Chand, Chainpur, Nuaon and Bhagwanpur, occupied the high category ranging between in terms of difference in percentage between male and female main workers. Ramgarh, Rampur, Kudra, Durgawati, Bhabua and Mohania occupied the very high category between 60-80 points.

Table 4: Category wise Male-female Differential in Main Workers (2011)

Male differential	female	% range	Number of blocks	Name of Blocks
Moderate		<40	1	Adhaura
High		40-60	4	Chand, Chainpur, Nuaon, Bhagwanpur,
Very high		61-80	6	Ramgarh, Rampur, Kudra, Durgawati, Bhabua, Mohania

Figure 3.

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

Male and Female Differential in Marginal workers

The total marginal worker in the district was 226517 in the year 2011. The table 3.10 shows that the blocks with largest population of Marginal workers are Bhabua (35087), Mohania, (27894), Chainpur (25462) and Ramgarh (22182). The lowest population of marginal worker was in Bhagwanpur block (11781) and Nuaon (12750). The largest percentage of women marginal worker was in Chainpur block (47.25%), Adhaura (44.59%), Chand (41.44%) and Ramgarh (40.14%). The gender gap was highest in Bhabua block (41.11%) and lowest in Chainpur block (5.49%)

Table 5: Block wise Male-female Differential in Marginal Workers in Kaimur District (2011)

Serial number	Block	Total workers	Male workers (%)	Female Workers (%)	Gender Gap
1	Ramgarh	22182	59.85	40.14	19.71
2	Nuaon	12750	61.41	38.6	22.81
3	Kudra	20815	61.13	38.86	22.27
4	Mohania	27894	64.31	35.7	28.61
5	Durgawati	16369	66.36	33.63	32.73
6	Chand	19288	58.55	41.44	17.11
7	Chainpur	25462	52.74	47.25	5.49
8	Bhabua	35087	70.55	29.44	41.11
9	Rampur	13860	60.37	39.62	20.75
10	Bhagwanpur	11781	66.44	33.55	32.89
11	Adhaura	18043	55.41	44.59	10.82
	District	226517	62.12	37.87	24.25

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

All the blocks can be divided into five categories on the basis of gender differential in the marginal workers. Table no. 3.11 shows that, the first category of very low gap was occupied by Chainpur block. The second category of low differential was found in three blocks namely Ramgarh, Chand and Adhaura having differential between 10-20. The third category is characterised by moderate differential ranging between 20-30 and has four blocks namely, Nuaon, Kudra, Mohania and Rampur. Durgawati and Bhagwanpur occupied the high differential category ranging between 30-40. Only Bhabua block occupied the category of very high differential above 40.

Table 6: Category wise Male-female Differential in Marginal Workers in Kaimur District (2011)

Category of Male-female differential	% range	Number of blocks	Name of Blocks
Very low	< 10	1	Chainpur
Low	10-20	3	Ramgarh, Chand, Adhaura
Moderate	20-30	4	Nuaon, Kudra, Mohania, Rampur
High	30-40	2	Durgawati, Bhagwanpur
Very high	>40	1	Bhabua

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

Figure - 4

and Female Differential in Non-workers

The total population of non-workers in the district is 11,15,221 which is 68.57 percent of the total population. Table no. 7 shows the male- female differential in non-working population in the year 2011. The percentage of non-working females to the total number of non-workers was highest in Bhabua (58.8%), Durgawati (58.8%), Mohania (58.31%), and Kudra (58.01%). The lowest percentage of non-workers in total population of non-workers was lowest in the Adhaura block. (53.6%)

Table 7: Block wise Male-female Differential in Non – Workers in Kaimur District (2011)

Serial number	Area	Total Nonworkers	Male Non-workers (%)	Female Non-Workers (%)	Gender Gap
1	Ramgarh	89784	42.29	57.70	15.41
2	Nuaon	71559	43	57	14
3	Kudra	114320	42	58.01	16
4	Mohania	160374	41.7	58.31	16.61
5	Durgawati	97610	41.20	58.8	17.6
6	Chand	87327	43.7	56.31	12.61
7	Chainpur	123216	43.13	56.9	13.77
8	Bhabua	177876	41.2	58.8	17.6
9	Rampur	60897	42.5	57.50	15
10	Bhagwanpur	62244	42	58	16
11	Adhaura	32393	46.4	53.6	7.2
	District	1115221	42.24	57.8	15.56

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

The Adhaura block registered the lowest gap in male and female non workers. Table no. 3.13 shows that Chand, Chainpur, Nuaon and Rampur had a moderate gap in between the female and male non workers. High gap between female and male nonworking population was in Ramgarh, Kudra, Bhagwanpur, Mohania, Durgawati and Bhabua.

Table 8: Category wise Male-female Differential in Non – Workers in Kaimur District (2011)

Category of Male female differential	% Range	Number of blocks	Name of Blocks
Low	<10	1	Adhaura
Moderate	10-15	4	Chand (12.61),Chainpur (13.77), Nuaon (14), Rampur(15)
High	>15	6	Ramgarh(15.41),Kudra(16), Bhagwanpur (16), Mohania (16.61), Dur gawati (17.6), Bhabua (17.6)

Source – Computed from District Census Handbook, Kaimur, 2001 and 2011

Conclusion

The participation of females in economic activities throws light on the economic status of females. Out of the total working population, 26.45 percent are females. The gender gap between male and female workers is 47.41 points in the district which is even higher in the case of main workers i.e. 65.6. This is because of engagement of females in the household activities which does not allow them to act as main workers. The blocks with highest differential between male and female workers were Mohania, Bhabua and Durgawati. The blocks with lowest differential in main workers were Adhaura Chand and Chainpur. The gender gap in marginal workers is low i.e. 24.25 points. It is very high in blocks like Chainpur,

Ramgarh, Chand and low in blocks Bhabua, Bhagwanpur and Durgawati. The number of non-working females far outnumber the number of non-working males and this is highest in blocks Bhabua, Durgawati and Mohania and lowest in Adhaura, Chand and Chainpur. This shows that there is large scale gender disparity in the study area.

The gender disparity in the workforce is undoubtedly a persistent challenge that is not only affecting the growth and development of females in the area but also the entire social podium. Despite positive interventions by the government, there still lies numerous setbacks in the form of unequal pay, lack of awareness about rights, full liability of household chores, social pressures etc. create a negative space and discourage the women from entering the economic landscape of the area. In order to make them enter the mainstream, steps should be taken by the government, organisations, activists etc. to promote equality and equity. The workforce can be made diverse and a perfect representative of the society only through a sustained commitment to gender equality.

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